

IN-LINE MONITORING AND NUMERICAL VERIFICATION OF RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING PROCESS WITH CYCOM® 890 RTM RESIN SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

An industrial scale Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) manufacturing trial was performed, injecting Cytec CYCOM®890 RTM resin system into 5-Harness Satin carbon preforms utilising in-line monitoring technology to validate numerical predictions. As the RTM process uses a metallic mould, visual inspection cannot be used for validation, hence the paper assesses the applicability of dielectric sensors for this purpose. The reasons for and potential benefits of using off-line simulation to define the manufacturing process are summarised in this paper, specifically in relation to the simulation of the RTM process. The results of simulations are used to aid and enhance mould design, optimise inlet and vent gate position and geometry, and to control the flow front and part quality. The paper describes and demonstrates the effectiveness of simulation technology applied to the RTM manufacturing process. Off line simulation of the cure process is performed in order to understand and define appropriate heat flow and cure development for CYCOM® 890 RTM. Numerical results are then compared with experiments performed with an industrial set-up of the RTM process. The paper describes in-line monitoring using dielectric sensor technology and robust modelling of flow front advancement and degree of cure development in a flat panel case and its assessment in a complex shape geometry part where the robustness of the numerical prediction is tested.

1 INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of the core project undertaken at the National Composites Centre is to develop and validate a methodology for the numerical simulation of the Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) process known as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM).

The aim of the project is to establish numerical simulation techniques with sufficient fidelity that they can be employed in the early stages of component design, thereby aiding the design of robust manufacturing processes.

Secondary aims of the project include the identification of technologies suitable for the monitoring of resin infusion and curing processes and the identification of opportunities to identify and establish standardised methods for the characterisation of various material parameters.

The quality of the parts manufactured using Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process is greatly affected by the process strategy, defined in terms of the injection scheme, and tool temperature cycle amongst other variables. As such, determining this strategy is an essential part of the design process. Since the costs associated with RTM tooling can be large, there is an increased focus on the role of simulation within RTM process definition. Although a number of RTM simulation tools have been developed, in general the aerospace industry has been slow to adopt this technology, due in part to the lack of proven methodology and industrial precedents.

The simulation of RTM processes can be used to assist and enhance the tooling design and process strategy, through the analysis of inlet and vent gate type and location, tool heating strategy, and injection pressures. Such parameters are defined in order to control the resin flow front and avoid dry spots, optimise the injection time, understand tool heat flux and avoid excessive exothermic temperatures. The simulation of RTM process can be used to optimise the cure cycle time, and ultimately qualitatively optimise part quality. In addition to this, the project will explore the potential benefits of real time monitoring of RTM processes, as, although beyond the scope of current work, the long term goal is to enable closed loop process control. Currently, the baseline measurement technique for cure development involves destructive measurement of the manufactured part such as Dynamic Mechanical Analyser (DMA) test.

Almost all numerical models for resin injection during the RTM processes are based around finite element implementations of Darcy's law, a phenomenological equation describing the flow of a fluid through a porous medium [1]. The fundamental material data required for the simulation is the permeability tensor of the reinforcement in the principal directions, in addition to the resin system rheology. The simulation of the cure process requires additional resin cure kinetics data, and various thermal properties of the tool and reinforcement [2].

This project aims to validate numerical models of RTM processes, in terms of two main variables; the resin flow front progression and cure development. Due to the nature of the RTM process, visual inspection is not feasible, so real time monitoring of the process is required. Initially, manufacturing trials will be conducted on simple, flat geometry, in order to verify the monitoring technology. After this stage of the project, trials on a more complex geometry will be conducted, to further determine the capability of the numerical models. The complex geometry to be used in this project can be seen below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Complex Geometry Part.

2 RESIN INFUSION AND CURE MONITORING TECHNOLOGY

The first stage of this project comprised of a technology assessment of monitoring technologies applicable for resin infusion and cure monitoring, the following section provides a summary of this work.

In order to meet the requirements of the project, the NCC was searching for an industry proven, commercially available monitoring system ensuring compatibility with proposed material and tooling

arrangements. A large range of technologies were considered including dielectric, D.C. electric, fibre optic and ultrasonic systems.

Potential systems were scored against several key requirements as shown below:

- Availability of calibration data for proposed resin systems
- System lead time
- Cost of system hardware, and technical support
- Applicability of sensor housing to tooling design
- Ability to monitor state of cure, in addition to temperature and resin flow front arrival
- Sensor dimensionality; the number of spatial dimensions a sensor is able monitor
- Level of proven industrial experience

A down selection matrix was used to rank the available systems against the list of requirements. The selection matrix showed that the dielectric system provided by ADVISE, was the most suitable system for the project; primarily because of the extensive experience associated with the system and extensive technical support for the duration of the planned test schedule. The system also scored highly on the applicability of the sensors to the tooling design because of the smaller geometric dimensions of the sensors compared with alternative systems.

The DC electric based monitoring system was also promising for the project, offering a suitable alternative to the ADVISE system. The main disadvantage of the system was the requirement of multiple data acquisition systems making the data collection process more complex.

Regarding the working principle of selected dielectric sensors and their integration into NCC RTM moulds, the process is described in this section. The set of experimental results collected and the comparison with numerical values is described in following section 4.

Today there is a need for technically robust, practically usable and industrially sustainable technologies for monitoring the resin condition throughout the process cycle in order to ensure quality manufacturing of composites structures. Among the available process monitoring technologies, dielectric sensing is closest to achieving the above mentioned qualities as it combines ease of installation and use, robustness and reproducibility of signals, portability and low cost of measurement devices. The dielectric sensing system of ADVISE relies on a well-established design concept of interdigitated microelectrodes. The latest design of these microelectrodes, which are printed grids of a metal conductor embedded in durable ceramic substrate, are adapted to small housings with integrated thermocouple for attachment to RTM moulds as shown in Figure 2. The electric field created at the sensor excitation probes the charged species and results in an informative response.

Figure 2. Durable interdigital microelectrode (left) and housing for attachment to moulds (right) suitable for monitoring RTM processes

The electrical signal can be converted to conductivity (a material property) via an appropriate sensor calibration function. The utility of the method relies on the correlation of conductivity to the resin viscosity in liquid state via a generic model with resin specific parameters and the correlation of conductivity to the resin degree of cure in post-gel state via a generic model with resin specific parameters. The parameters of these models for Cycom 890RTM resin were defined by ADVISE and were loaded to the measurement software, so that on-line estimation of viscosity and degree of cure

was performed. The real-time processing of conductivity data at the sensor locations provided accurate indication of resin arrival at these locations and accurate estimation of the resin viscosity during the mould filling process.

A new design of durable sensor was designed and manufactured for the manufacturing trials. The sensors were directly integrated into the RTM tooling, the design allowed for easy installation and removal as shown in Figure 3. In order to prevent short-circuiting of the sensor element, the sensor surface was covered by a thin layer of glass fibre cloth.

Figure 3: Sensors system and plug to be used when the sensor is not assembled into the mould

3 MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION

The first stage of the project involved the characterisation of the materials used during the manufacturing trials. The resin system CYCOM 890-RTM manufactured by Cytec was chosen due to the availability of characterisation data available in open literature. A woven fabric (5-Harness Satin Weave Carbon Fibre Fabric) was selected as the reinforcement material.

The only material characterisation tests carried out specifically for this project were permeability tests of the reinforcement. The rest of the data was sourced through open literature.

Both in-plane and through thickness permeability measurements were conducted at the University of Nottingham, in order to characterise the material. The in-plane permeability is characterised in unsaturated radial injection experiments at constant injection pressure. Determination of the principal permeability values, K_1 and K_2 , is based on measurement of the extent of the flow front ellipse along the given principal axes as a function of time [6]. The through-thickness permeability of the fabric was determined in saturated uni-directional flow experiments at constant volume flow rate. Measurement of the pressure drop across the specimen allows the calculation of through thickness permeability to be made.

The resin system to be used throughout the project is Cytec CYCOM 890 RTM; the data sheet for this resin is available at the Cytec website. Regarding dielectric characterisation of the resin system: ADVISE is already in possession of the necessary calibration data for CYCOM 890 RTM, and as such no further material characterisation testing is required. Due to the proprietary nature of this data, details of the model cannot be published in this report.

A PhD thesis studying the characterisation of CYCOM 890 RTM was used as a source for all of the cure kinetics data [3]. The work used a thermo-analytical technique known as Differential Scanning Calorimetry, in order to create a cure model for the resin system

The data collected during the DSC experiments was used to create an autocatalytic cure model, developed by Hubert et al [4], for the resin, CYCOM 890-RTM. The form of the Hubert model is shown below in equation (1);

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = K \frac{\alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n}{1 + \exp[C(\alpha - (\alpha_{CO} + \alpha_{CT}T))]} \quad (1)$$

K is a rate constant, following an Arrhenius temperature dependency shown in equation (2), α is the degree of cure, $\delta\alpha/\delta t$ is the rate of reaction, T is temperature, and $m, n, C, \alpha_{CO}, \alpha_{CT}$ are constants.

$$K = A \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (2)$$

Unfortunately, the Hubert model is not one of the standard cure models available within PAM-RTM 2014.5, a simulation software package produced by ESI designed for Liquid Composite Moulding process simulation used to create the numerical models used throughout this work, as such, the user has to create a custom C++ script in order to generate a User dll function. The details of this process are fully explained in the PAM-RTM User Guide and Tutorial information [5]. Additional IF statements are required to ensure the kinetics model does not yield number error as alpha approaches one, as this will cause the simulation to exit with an error.

As an alternative, the data from the DSC experiments described in the thesis was used to create a cure model that was pre-defined within PAM-RTM [5]. This was done using a linear regression implemented using Excel.

The model used is Kamal-Sourour that takes the form shown below:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \left(A_1 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_1}{T}\right) + A_2 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_1}{T}\right) \cdot \alpha^m \right) (B - \alpha)^n \quad (3)$$

This model can be implemented into PAM-RTM more easily, as the model is pre-loaded and a custom script is not required.

Figures 4 and 5 display the results of the Kamal-Sourour and Hubert models, as well as the experimental data points. Both models show fairly good correlation with the data points, however the Hubert model displays a better fit with the experimental data, as such the Hubert model was used throughout the simulation detailed within this report.

Figure 4: Cure Kinetics Models – Degree of Cure as a Function of Time and Temperature.

Figure 5: Cure Kinetics Models – Cure Rate as a Function of Degree of Cure and Temperature.

Initially a rheology model from literature was used in the numerical simulations; the work was part of the same PhD thesis that documented the cure kinetics functions [3]. The results from the first phase of manufacturing trials indicated that this rheology model was not appropriate for the resin system; the

viscosity model appeared to be an order of magnitude too high. As such, a Castro-Macosko model was created using linear regression techniques as this is one of the rheology models pre-loaded into PAM-RTM. The data used to create this model was sourced from the resin manufacturer's data sheet. The model takes the form of the equation shown below in equation (3), where V is viscosity, α is degree of cure, T is temperature, and C_0, C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 are model fitting constants.

$$V = c_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{c_1}{T}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_2}{c_2 - \alpha}\right)^{c_3 + c_4 \cdot \alpha} \quad (3)$$

In order to model the heat transfer during the RTM process, two thermal properties of the resin are required; the thermal conductivity, and specific heat capacity. PAM-RTM has the capability to model these parameters as constant values, a function of temperature, or a function of temperature and cure state.

The Cytec data sheet contained no values for either of these properties; as such values from the MATWEB online database for generic epoxy resins were used. Both parameters were defined as constant values, since no further data was available.

Other properties of the resin system such as density were used directly from the manufacturer's data sheet.

4 METHODOLOGY

This section of the report describes the methodology used during the manufacturing trials. The geometry of both the flat panel and the complex part is also described in this section.

In order to test the monitoring system, and provide a baseline comparison between numerical and experimental results for a case with simple geometry, a number of manufacturing trials were conducted with a flat panel RTM tool, with line injection and vent gates located at either end of the tool. Four dielectric sensors were positioned along the centre line of the tool at equally spaced intervals. This section of the report details the experimental procedure.

A schematic of the complex shape RTM tool is shown in Figure 7. The conceptual tooling design was completed by the tooling department within the NCC, numerical simulations were used to verify important design decisions such as inlet/outlet gate location however the majority of design tasks were completed using experience and established methods.

The shape of the complex part is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 5. The part is approximately 384 mm in length, however this is intended as a reference only; the overall length of the component is dictated by the ramp angles. The component is 180 mm wide.

Figure 5: Complex geometry RTM mould schematic

The layup used is shown in Figure 6; the thinnest section in the centre of the geometry comprises of 10 layers of fabric, all of these plies run the entire length of the part, 5 along the top, and 5 along the bottom. The ply drop off is then completed as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: complex geometry Layup

A schematic of the tooling used to manufacture this complex geometry is shown below in Figure 7. The injection strategy comprises of an injection gate along the entire width of the thick section of the component. Vacuum ports are located in the centre and end of the component. Dielectric sensors are located along the mid-plane of the component, equally spaced along the rear face avoiding the additional blanking plate, and L-section.

Figure 7: complex geometry mould schematic

The tool surface and sensor surfaces were released using Frekote 770. The fabric was cut to size using the ply cutter before being laid up by hand. The material was handled as little as possible in order not to damage the fabric and alter the permeability. A hot de-bulk procedure was performed for all manufacturing trials utilising the complex geometry.

The resin injection process was implemented as follows; resin was pre-heated in an oven before being transferred to the injection equipment at 80°C. The pressure pot within the machine was heated to maintain the resin temperature. Before injection the resin was degassed for 30 minutes.

The injection process began after the tooling had reached the prescribed temperature of 120°C. The pressure in the pressure pot was increased to 1 [bar] (Absolute Pressure) and the inlet valve was opened. The vent valve was kept open until resin reached the trap pot, indicating a sufficient level of resin bleed, after which, the vent valve was then closed, and the injection pressure was increased to 3 [bar].

The tool temperature was maintained at 180°C for the duration of the cure cycle; for a total dwell time of 120 minutes. After the point at which the resin was expected to gel; 50 minutes into the total dwell time, the injection valve was closed, and the injection equipment disconnected.

5 NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

The numerical models used in this work were created with PAM-RTM, a simulation software package produced by ESI designed for Liquid Composite Moulding process simulation. The software is based around three fundamental phenomena; resin flow through the fibrous reinforcement material, heat transfer between various sections of the tool, resin and reinforcement, and finally the chemical process of the resin during cure. The software does not model any mechanical effects of the process [5].

Resin flow through the reinforcement material is considered as flow through a porous medium, described by Darcy's law; flow rate per unit area is proportional to the pressure gradient and inversely proportional to viscosity, shown below.

$$\vec{V} = -\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla P \quad (4)$$

In this equation, V is the fluid velocity, μ is the fluid viscosity, P is pressure, and K is the permeability tensor. In order to conserve the mass of fluid, the system must also satisfy the divergence condition shown below;

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{V} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Dirichlet boundary conditions are used to specify the problem, by specifying the pressure at inlet/outlet boundaries.

The material permeability is a physical property of the material that is determined experimentally. A spatial permeability tensor is used to define the material permeability in its principal directions.

Thermal behaviour of the system has a large influence on the physical behaviour of the resin flow and cure stages since temperature determines many of the resin's properties such as viscosity and polymerisation reactivity. Heat transfer occurs by means of conduction between the fibres of reinforcement, resin, and tool material, convection is also present during the filling stages of the process, and finally the resin polymerisation is an exothermic chemical reaction, and therefore produces heat. PAM-RTM solves the temperature field in the model by means of the following general equation;

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_r c_{pr} \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T = \nabla \cdot [k \cdot \nabla T] - p_r \Delta h \frac{D\alpha}{Dt} \quad (6)$$

Where T is temperature, t represents time, ρ is density, C_p is the specific heat, k is the heat conduction coefficient tensor, α is state of cure, and Δh total enthalpy of polymerisation. The subscript r is used to designate the resin (7).

As mentioned above, the viscosity of resin is strongly coupled its temperature, and degree of polymerisation. Because of this, PAM-RTM offers several constitutive equations for modelling viscosity, the user also has the ability to code an alternative model in C++.

In a similar manner, the kinetics of the resin polymerisation reaction is modelled as a function of temperature and state of cure. There are several in-built models in PAM-RTM centred on the Kamal-Sourour model. As with the rheology, the user has the ability to use a custom model, implemented by running a custom script.

Geometry was created using CATIA, and imported into Visual Environment, an ESI developed suite of simulation software. The meshing of the solid geometry was completed within Visual Mesher. The PAM-RTM solver is only capable of using triangle and tetrahedral elements for infusion simulations; as such models were created on this basis.

Numerical models for the resin injection process were created without tooling geometry, since this process is largely isothermal; any thermal inertia of the tooling is insignificant.

The majority of numerical models used for cure simulations were created inclusive of the tool geometry, in order to account for the thermal effects of the tooling. The complex geometry part was modelled using a three dimensional mesh as shown in Figure 8, the 3D mould mesh is not visible.

Figure 8: 3D Numerical cure Model Mesh

Numerical models aimed at understanding the injection process had to account for the layup of the complex part. As discussed in the previous section, the layup used in the complex geometry is shown in Figure 6; the thinnest section in the centre of the geometry comprises of 10 layers of fabric, all of these plies run the entire length of the part. In order to correctly model this with PAM-RTM, the geometry was split up into several zones as shown in Figure 9. Each zone then has a separate definition of the permeability tensor in order to represent the layup structure. The model was split in this way before it was meshed, so as to preserve the zone definitions when the model was transferred into PAM-RTM.

Figure 9: 3D Numerical cure Model Mesh

It was decided to manufacture the part with fabric layer all aligned in the same direction $[0^\circ]$, as this is the manner in which the permeability measurements were conducted. Using PAM-RTM there are currently two ways in which multi-directional layups can be modelled.

The first method makes use of the laminate functionality within PAM-RTM. The software models different stacking sequences by applying homogenous permeability vectors to the entire region. The average permeability tensor is calculated using the thickness and quantity of each layer. Since the permeability of each layer is actually a tensor, the permeability tensor of each layer is transformed to the principal directions of the first ply. The resulting non-diagonal permeability matrix is then diagonalised; the final principal directions of the laminate are the eigenvectors of the non-diagonal matrix, while the magnitudes of the permeability are the eigenvalues. This permeability tensor is then applied to the entire region. Because of this, the flow behaviour will not show variation through the thickness; it would be the average representation of the flow.

An alternative modelling technique is to split the model up into separate zones representing each ply, different permeability vectors can then be applied to each layer individually depending on the ply orientation. Using this method, the flow structure in each ply will be captured.

The problem with both techniques is the assumption that the through thickness permeability does not depend on the layup structure. In reality the through thickness permeability will be different for a stack of $[0^\circ]$ plies opposed to a sequence of $[+45^\circ, -45^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ]$.

6 RESULTS

This section of the report documents the results of all of the numerical models and manufacturing trials completed as part of this project. The section is split up into the two phases of manufacturing trials; the flat panel trials, and complex geometry trials.

The first trial suffered a large amount of resin release from the tool during the cure stage of the cycle. As a result, the final part quality was very poor, as the preform was not fully wet. Despite this, the monitoring system was still able to capture useful information on the resin flow, and curing stages. The second trial was completed without any errors, and produced a good standard of part.

Figure 10 shows the results for the first manufacturing trial, the graph displays the distance of the resin flow-front as a function of time. Plotted on the graph is the experimental results, and PAM-RTM results.

It was assumed that the resin temperature was 120°C by the time it reached the cavity, as the tool temperature was 120°C. The experimental results show very good agreement with these results. A linear regression was used to fit Darcy’s law to the experimental results.

Figure 10 also shows the results from the second experimental trail, due to the differing injection pressures between trials, the results have been plotted on separate graphs. Again the experimental results fit the numerical results very well.

Figure 10: Flow Front Development Numerical/Experimental Results Comparison

Figures 11 and 12 show the evolution of the logarithmic conductivity values measured by the sensors during the first and second manufacturing trials using the flat panel tooling. As soon as the temperature of the tooling reached the required injection temperature, around 120 min on the graph, resin was injected in the tool. The conductivity values jumped sequentially as resin reached each sensor in the mould. The conductivity values remain high during the period in which the tooling was heated to the final cure temperature. Following the point of resin arrival, the conductivity values are converted to viscosity values so that the evolution of resin viscosity can be monitored in real time.

As soon as the resin reached the final cure temperature, the conductivity data were used to estimate the evolution of the degree of cure. The polymerisation reaction progress reduces the mobility of charged species, ions and dipoles, within the resin. This causes the conductivity to drop, as the cure progresses. The conductivity levels out to a level that is indicative of the final degree of cure. During the first manufacturing trial, Figure 11, the measured degree of cure from sensors is overall in good agreement with the predictions made by the numerical models, as shown in Figure 13. The final conductivity values across the four sensors show a small variation.

Figure 11: Conductivity data, phase 1 Trial 1

At the second manufacturing trial, the same behaviour was observed; however, the conductivity data during the late stages of cure show a sudden drop at two discrete time intervals. The physical reason for this behaviour is currently under investigation, although it is thought to be due to the part separating from the sensor surface due to shrinkage during cure.

Figure 12: Conductivity data, phase 1 Trial 2

Figure 13 shows the results for degree of cure from the first manufacturing trial. The sensors started determining the degree of cure at the point at which the temperature reached the final cure temperature. The final degree of cure was attained at different times for each individual sensor location. This effect was not seen in the numerical model, and is thought to be errors associated with the experimental measurements.

Figure 13: Degree of Cure Results Flat panel RTM Trial 2

7 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the comparison between the numerical results and experimental values for flow front development in the case of the flat panel tooling, showed good agreement. The validity of the numerical predictions in a more complex geometry is currently under investigation. The complex geometry will assess the numerical models ability to model resin flow in three dimensions, as well as assessing the through thickness permeability measurements.

The cure data obtained from sensors show also good overall agreement with the predictions obtained through numerical modelling.

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